

Reproducibility Study: On Heavy-User Bias in A/B Testing

Examination of Three Different Papers in Respect to Reproducibility and Reproduction of Selected One

Matthias Hofmaier

TU Wien

Vienna, Austria

e11944050@student.tuwien.ac.at

Johanna Schneider

TU Wien

Vienna, Austria

e1227158@student.tuwien.ac.at

Ahmadou Wagne

TU Wien

Vienna, Austria

e12002293@student.tuwien.ac.at

ABSTRACT

There are many challenges in reproducing experiments in computational sciences. Often the code or the data used are not openly available. Sometimes seemingly smaller factors are not reported on, like operating machines, versions of programming languages and packages, hyper parameters and even random seeds used.

In this report, within the scope of the final project of the course "Experiment Design for Data Science" at TU Wien in the fall semester 2020/21, we examined three papers of our choice regarding their reproducibility and tried to reproduce one of them.

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CCS CONCEPTS

• **Mathematics of computing** → *Hypothesis testing and confidence interval computation*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Model verification and validation*.

KEYWORDS

reproducibility, jackknife, heavy-user bias, a/b testing, experiment design, PRIMAD

1 INTRODUCTION

When trying to reproduce experiments in computational sciences, one might face many challenges. The most severe are the availability of the data and the original source code. But even if both are made available, the results still might not be reproducible. Functions in different programming languages or on different operating systems might have slight differences between them which could have a huge impact on the results. For example, random variables might be calculated differently. Also, updates in packages used - i.e. modifications of functions - could lead to different results. R. Mayer and A. Rauber [4] showed, that a majority of publicly shared scientific workflows are not re-executable.

For our final project in "Experiment Design for Data Science" at TU Vienna in the fall semester of 2020/21, we chose one paper each from the proceedings of SIGIR (International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval), CIKM (International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management) and ECIR (European Conference on Information Retrieval) respectively across the last 5 years. All papers were examined on their difficulty of reproducibility. The paper which seemed to be the most easily reproducible was chosen for reproduction. A detailed examination of the experimental setup was done and the results were put under scrutiny.

2 WIKIPEDIA TEXT REUSE: WITHIN AND WITHOUT

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15712-8_49

2.1 Summary

The paper from Alshomary, Völske et al., published in ECIR 19, deals with the reuse of text within and without Wikipedia [1]. For the within-analysis they obtained whole Wikipedia to compare it against itself. For the without-analysis they took a 10%-sample of the Common Crawl, which is an open repository for web crawl data. This results in 4.2 million articles consisting of 11.4 million paragraphs for the within-analysis and 1.4 million websites consisting of 591 million web pages with 187 million paragraphs for the without-analysis.

The task of text reuse detection can be divided into two sub-tasks, namely *source retrieval* and *text alignment*. Where *source retrieval* is retrieving a set of sources that are potentially reusing text for a given document and *text alignment* the mutual text passages for a given document pair. For *source retrieval* different hashing functions and different similarity measurements are used to rank document pairs regarding their similarity. To select the hashing function, similarity measurement and to tune hyperparameters, a ground truth was obtained by using the subsequent step of finer granular *text alignment* for 1000 long Wikipedia articles. Variational deep semantic hashing in combination with cosine similarity on tf-idf-weighted unigram representations showed the best results. The computational budget to do this were 2 months of processing time on a 130 node cluster running Apache Spark. For *text alignment* first short exact matches are identified (seed matching), these short matches are then extended via DBScan clustering to extract reused text spans. This process is repeated for all document combinations except for those that did not rank high enough in *source retrieval* or document combinations that exceed over 250 consecutive miss cases in seed generation.

The later analysis shows that there are 110 million cases of text reuse within Wikipedia and 1.6 million cases without. Averaging in 78 and 252 words per text reuse for within- and without-analysis. The detected reuse can be distinguished by to types: *structure reuse* and *content reuse*. Cases with *structure reuse* are articles where the same text structure is used with different facts (e.g. articles that describe cities). This type of reuse mostly occurs when two articles are vertically aligned. *Content reuse* are cases where articles contain almost identical text passages having the same content, this can occur within Wikipedia when articles have an inherent relationship (e.g. Tigers and Leopards are both cats). Where 87% of the reuse cases within Wikipedia are out of structural nature, the reused text accounts for more than 90% of the main content for

the found websites without Wikipedia. Most of these websites do not reference Wikipedia as a source, but display advertisements. To quantify the revenue possibly made with those advertisements, the authors estimate the monthly page view counts with 10% of those for the copied Wikipedia articles. With an average revenue per 1000 impressions (RPM) of 1.4 USD this results in a monthly revenue of 45,000 USD for reusing websites of the 10% Common Crawl sample. Extrapolated to the entire web, this results in 5.5 million USD estimates revenue per month, which corresponds to 72% of Wikipedia's fundraising returns in the whole year of 2018.

2.2 Reproducibility

The paper contains references for the used code¹ and the data² used to reproduce the experiment. Depending on where you access the paper, these references are included or not. Although code and data is available (in some of the publications), the reproduction of the results seems rather difficult. This is the case because the code is poorly commented and the naming in the code is not fully aligned with the mentioned functionalities in the paper. This makes it fairly hard to run the different experiment settings, because there is only documentation for one of the experiment settings provided. Because of the large amount of data used in the experiment, the code has to be executed on a Spark cluster. The repository contains a reference to a docker image for the suggested Spark execution environment. Unfortunately, this image appears to be offline and therefore causes further difficulties in reproduction. Also there are no random seeds included in the code. Even without all of the aforementioned challenges, the experiments are hardly reproducible just because of their huge processing time, which was estimated by the authors to take 2 months on a 130 node cluster.

3 ANALYZING AND PREDICTING NEWS POPULARITY IN AN INSTANT MESSAGING SERVICE

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3331184.3331301>

3.1 Summary

One paper we took into consideration is „Analyzing and Predicting News Popularity in an Instant Messaging Service“ by Mohammad Naseri and Hamed Zamani published in SIGIR' 19 [5]. The goal of this paper is to predict the popularity of news in the instant messaging service Telegram. As a measure for popularity the number of unique users that viewed a message is introduced. For that they consider news posts of different agencies published in a 7 month period. The goal is to predict the top 5% and 25% popular posts for each channel, so it can be viewed as an imbalanced binary classification task. The hypothesis is that there exists useful information that can be transferred between news agencies in order to improve predictions. In the following they use MTL CASO as a multi-task learning model that decomposes the model of each task in two components: task-specific and task-shared feature mappings. Furthermore for predictions they use a linear model, that optimizes a logistic loss function and assign higher weights to instances from

the minority class, as the distribution of data is highly skewed. For the experimental setup, the data is divided into training and test data in chronological order (first six months training and the last month test data). Each post gets a binary label („popular“ or „not popular“) based on the 5% or 25% threshold. In addition two single-task models are considered as baseline. Namely an SVM classifier that is trained for each channel and one that is trained on the data of all channels together. For those the hyper-parameter c was selected using 5-fold cross-validation over the training data. The results show that it is harder to predict the top 5% than the top 25%, as the lower the percentage, the more imbalanced the data and thus a bias towards the majority class is more likely. In conclusion the MTL method achieves the highest performance most of the time, while the SVM with all data pooled together often performs poorly. Another main finding is that balanced accuracy and the F1 tend to disagree in some cases, although they are common metrics for imbalanced classification tasks. So the model struggles to detect the popular posts, when the threshold is low, but detects most of the non-popular posts.

3.2 Reproducibility

Considering the reproduction of this paper, we first look at what is available and what is not. First of all the paper includes a link to a github repository, which contains the whole Telegram data set and also a Twitter data set³. The authors list that they used scikit-learn and MALSAR, as well as the methods they used, however they do not provide any code or specify anything about their exact implementations. They also state how they obtained e.g. the hyperparameter for the SVM and which features were used, but do not give specific information about numbers. For the comparison of the performance metrics, they focus on the raw numbers and list them in a table, to then decide on the best performance based on the best values and state that performance improved for multi-task learning. No statistical tests were made in the process. In conclusion, we have an outline of the working process here that definitely makes reproducing possible. We have all the data used, the methods used and results to compare. We also have the exact training and test split for the models, which doesn't require a random seed, as it is chronologically based. However we have no exact information about the above mentioned hyperparameters and the CV (which includes randomness). So with no code and no exact information about parts of the implementation, it is not possible to fully reproduce the findings, but it is feasible to produce results in the same fashion, to compare them to their findings. For further work one would additionally perform statistical tests, e.g. to show that the improvement in performance that was observed is significant.

4 ON HEAVY-USER BIAS IN A/B TESTING

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3357384.3358143>

4.1 Summary

To evaluate changes in software development, online experiments (also known as A/B Testing) are conducted, where users are randomly assigned to the treatment and control groups as they come

¹<https://github.com/webis-de/ECIR-19>

²<https://webis.de/data/webis-wikipedia-text-reuse-18.html>

³<https://github.com/IceCream71/TelegramNews>

Table 1: Notation

Notation	Explanation
$Y_u(t)$	the observed outcome of user u at day t
Z_u	whether user u is in the treatment group
$R_u(t)$	whether user u used the product on day t
$\tau_u(t)$	the treatment effect for user u on day t
$c_u(t)$	the control effect for user u on day t
k	length of experiment in days

online. The assignment remains consistent throughout the experiment and statistics about the user behaviour is collected. After the experiment, metrics for both groups are computed and statistical tests are conducted to detect differences in both groups.

However the question is, whether the external validity - the generalization of the results of the sample to the entire population - holds. It is known that factors like the novelty effect or the week-day/weekend effect influence external validity. Heavy-user bias is another important factor, which is examined in this paper by Wang, Gupta et al., which was published in the proceedings of CIKM 2019 [6]. For example: A website has 200 users, of which 100 visit the website every day (heavy-users) and the rest uses the website with probability 0.5 every day. If said website conducts an experiment for 1 day, the experiment would be run on 150 users of which 2/3 are heavy-users.

The authors of the paper prove that, under some mild assumptions, the heavy-user bias is inversely proportional to the length of the experiment and propose a re-sampling estimator for bias adjustment.

4.1.1 Assumptions.

- **Stable unit treatment assumption:** The outcome of any user is independent from the treatment of other users. This is reasonable when users don't interact with each other, but might break otherwise, i.e. social media.
- **super population:** The behavior of each user is an i.i.d. sample from a super population.
- **incremental experiment assumption:** The group assignments don't affect the users visits, so the frequency of the users visits does not change. This assumption is plausible, as most experiments do not affect the frequency of the users visits. However, this needs to be checked thoroughly before analyzing the data.

With the assumptions and the notation shown in Table 1, the observed outcome of the user u on day t is then defined as

$$Y_u(t) = R_u(t)\{Z_u\tau_u(t) + c_u(t)\}.$$

4.1.2 *Model.* To model user behaviour, a model based on fixed population with user heterogeneity is chosen.

- Whether a user u uses the product on day t is i.i.d. from a Bernoulli random variable with success probability $p \sim f(\cdot)$.
- The expectation of the treatment effect for user u is $\mathbb{E}\tau_u(t) = \tau(p)$. This implies that the treatment effect is different for users with different activity parameter p , but remains the same across all days.

- The expectation of the control outcome, analogously to the expectation of the treatment effect, is a function of p .

In the paper, the metrics computed to estimate the impact of the treatment is the scaled single average of the click-through rate which is defined as $\frac{1}{k}\mathbb{E}\{\sum_{t=1}^k Y_u(t)|Z_u = z\}$, ($z = 1, 0$). Other metrics are implemented in the code and discussed for further research.

The average treatment effect is defined as the difference between the metric of the treatment group and the control group

$$\Delta_{\text{scaled}} = \mathbb{E}\left\{\frac{1}{k}\sum_{t=1}^k R_u(t)\tau_u(t)\right\},$$

which can be estimated from the observed data ($\hat{\Delta}_{\text{scaled}}$). Finally, the heavy user bias is defined as

$$\mathbb{E}(\hat{\Delta}_{\text{scaled}}) - \Delta_{\text{scaled}}$$

which - under the model assumptions - is shown to be equivalent to $\Delta_{\text{scaled}}f(0) \cdot k^{-1} + O(k^{-2})$.

The authors of the paper propose a bias-adjusted estimator inspired by jackknife, to replace $\hat{\Delta}_{\text{scaled}}$. The idea is that for a fixed experiment duration k , the true value of the outcome a and its estimate $h(k)$, the heavy user bias can be approximated as a function of k : $h(k) - a = b/k + O(k^{-2})$. Now two points, $h(k)$ and $h(k-1)$ can be used to estimate a as $\hat{a} = k \cdot h(k) - (k-1) \cdot h(k-1)$.

In the case of the paper, $\hat{\Delta}_{\text{scaled}}$ is substituted for $h(k)$. Substituting $h(k-1)$ analogously could lead to high variance, since not all data is used. Therefore it is computed by leaving out each day once and averaging the results.

This procedure results in the bias-adjusted estimate $\hat{\Delta}_{\text{jack}}$. With this adjusted estimate the heavy-user bias is inversely proportional to the length of the experiment $\mathbb{E}\hat{\Delta}_{\text{jack}} - \Delta_{\text{scaled}} = O(k^{-2})$.

The bias adjusted estimator was tested by simulating two models. In the first one, the user behaviour was strictly modeled under the model assumptions described above. In the second model, user behaviour contained some novelty effect, which violates the user behaviour model.

For both models the experiments were simulated to last for 14 days and the maximum number of units in each group was 1000 (some users might not use the product throughout the experiment, which was taken into consideration). The ground truth Δ_{scaled} was set to be 1/3. For each model the data generating process was repeated 100 times. Each time the naive difference in means estimator, the bias adjusted estimator and a block bootstrap estimator [3] were computed. On average, the bias adjusted estimator produced the smallest bias in the experiment.

4.2 Reproducibility

The source code for the experiment was made available by the authors and can directly be downloaded as a Jupyter Notebook from GitHub⁴. The simulations for the data are part of the Notebook, so the data is also available. However, no random seed was used, so the results of the Jupyter Notebook slightly differ from the results in the paper, but were still within reason. Although the experiment

⁴<https://github.com/shifwang/On-Heavy-user-Bias-in-AB-Testing>

steps are covered in the paper, it is not indicated which set-up, such as operating system and specific version of Python, was used. All parameters needed for their analysis are given in the code and paper, although some parameters seem to be set arbitrarily, like the number of days and especially the parameter for the ground truth Δ_{scaled} , which will be discussed in the next section.

The authors repeated the data generating process 100 times, calculated the bias for the three different estimates and reported the mean bias, but failed to do a significance test.

Since the code and the data was made publicly available, it seems to be relatively easy to reproduce.

5 REPRODUCING EXPERIMENT

Since both the source code and the data for the experiment of the paper "On Heavy-user Bias in A/B testing" is publicly available and the experiment was coded in Python3, a programming language which we all feel comfortable with, we decided to reproduce this experiment.

5.1 Hypothesis

The original hypothesis formulated by the authors in the paper is that their proposed jackknife estimator outperforms a naive approach and the so called bootstrap estimator [3] in estimating the average treatment effect for an A/B testing experiment on simulated data. The independent variable of the hypothesis is the used estimator. The dependent variable is the respective estimation of the average treatment effect. As controls of the experiment the following settings are utilised:

- **Setting A:** Naive Estimator.
- **Setting B:** Bootstrap Estimator.
- **Setting C:** Jackknife Estimator.
- Every other aspect is identical when running the experiment.

The performance criterion is the mean difference to a fixed ground truth over 100 randomized simulations. Under the assumption that the generated data is representative for the task, estimate the average treatment effect (ATE) with the naive estimator, estimate the ATE with the bootstrap estimator and estimate the ATE with the jackknife estimator for 100 simulations. If the mean difference to the ground truth is the lowest for the jackknife estimator, the hypothesis is confirmed. The hypothesis was tested with two data models. One under strict model assumptions and another data model that takes the novelty effect into account.

5.2 Strategy

Based on our observations of their approach, we then built a strategy to reproduce and challenge the results based on the PRIMAD model of Freire, Fuhr and Rauber [2]. The first component that was primed here was of course the Actor, as we simply took the existing code and ran it for ourselves. This leads to the finding that there was no random seed and thus the results slightly differed to the reported values in the paper. But other than that, there were no issues when running the cited code. Considering the raw data, it was already stated, that it is simulated and that we can not reproduce the exact same input, so this is automatically primed for every run that does not use the same seed. As far as parameters go the authors neither included possible variations of extraneous variables (like

number of replications, experiment duration k or distribution size), which could possibly affect the dependent variable, nor explained sufficiently why certain values were chosen and fixed.

Thus, we decided to build a parameter grid with different values for:

- **Seed:** [1, 42, 420]
- **Number of replications:** [10, 50, 100, 200]
- **Distribution size:** [500, 1000, 2000]
- **Experiment duration:** [7, 14, 28, 56]

and repeated the simulation for each combination of those, which results in 144 parameter combinations for each data model. This leads to the next component that was scrutinized which is the Implementation. Thus we wrapped the provided simulation code into a function, to simplify the experimenting with the different parameters and parameter grids like the mentioned above. However the core implementation of the algorithm was not changed, it was basically just expanded.

To test if the hypothesis holds under different circumstances, the various extraneous variables were basically included as dependent variables and so the Method was primed. Considering the Method another aspect to challenge the hypothesis is the following. In the original paper the experiments were simulated 100 times (number of replications) each and the bias of the three different estimates was computed each time. Only the mean values and the standard errors were reported but the code also included box plots. No significance test was conducted, which was a flaw in our eyes. Since the different bias reported are computed from the same data, they are not independent from each other. Therefore, we decided to add a paired sample t-test for the difference in means. The box plot of the bias showed that the data was normally distributed without huge outliers and the reported standard errors were nearly the same, so the assumptions for the paired t-test are met.

As our goal was to see if the findings of the paper still hold under different conditions of the extraneous variables (because they were fixed/arbitrary for the shown experiments), we also tested the re-use of the Research objective under changing settings, because turning those extraneous variables into independents essentially leads to new hypotheses.

The last thing that should be mentioned is that there is no information about the Platform and the environment used for executing the provided code, so we lack information about OS, Python version and the version of Jupyter notebook. For future references, the environment under which we conducted our experiments can be found in the readme file in the github repository containing our code⁵.

In the following sections the findings and exact methods used for each step will be discussed.

5.3 Results

As already mentioned above, we ran 144 simulations with different parameters for each data model and then performed a paired t-test for both jackknife estimator vs. naive estimator and jackknife estimator vs. bootstrap estimator.

First of all we started to analyse the distribution of p-values of the t-test statistics for both estimators.

⁵<https://github.com/mjhof/edds-paper-reproduction>

Figure 1: Distribution of t-test p-values for jackknife vs. naive estimator (left) and jackknife vs. bootstrap estimator (right).

As you can see in figure 1, there are some more small p-values when testing against the naive estimator. Both distributions are strongly left skewed. The mean p-value for the naive estimator is 9.67×10^{-4} with standard deviation 9.74×10^{-3} and the mean p-value for the bootstrap estimator is 6.83×10^{-3} with a standard deviation of 3.122×10^{-2} . The distributions of the p-values indicate that the differences in means are over all significant. This can also be seen in figure 2, where the 5 most significant parameter settings of the simulations are depicted. We can see that the results tend

Figure 2: Top 5 most significant simulations for both data models.

to be more significant for a short experiment duration k . This also underlines the assumption of the authors, that user bias in A/B testing is inversely proportional to the length of the experiment [6]. The difference in means for those simulations tends to be high and the p-value tends to be low. The inverse can be observed for simulations with a long experiment duration. Figure 3 depicts the 5 least significant simulations. Here we can see a low difference in means and a high p-value. Also, the least significant simulations had a lower number of replications and a smaller distribution size. If we reject all simulations with a p-value higher than 5×10^{-2} (significance level of 5%), we end up with 2 not significant simulations for jackknife vs. naive estimator and 11 not significant simulations for jackknife vs. bootstrap estimator. However, it is debatable whether

Figure 3: Top 5 least significant simulations for both data models.

such a small number of replications is sufficient. The highest correlating parameters (Pearson correlation) in respect to the significance are the number of replications (sample size, i.e. N), followed by negative k and the distribution size. Different seeds and the two used data models don't seem to affect the simulations.

5.4 Ground Truth

In the original experiment, the ground truth Δ_{scaled} is set to be $1/3$. For each data generating process, the estimators are computed and the bias - the difference between the estimator and the true value - are computed. However, the true value does not influence the data generating process, so a different ground truth does not influence the estimation thereof. In addition, the bias is not calculated as the absolute value of the difference and can therefore take negative values. Thus a change of the ground truth results only in a shift of the bias. If the ground truth is set to be higher, for example $1/2$, the mean values for the bias fall below 0. Since the values stemming from the jackknife estimator are the smallest, it is no longer the best estimator with the smallest bias.

However, the question whether the bias should be expressed as an absolute value lies beyond our capabilities. Therefore, we did not include the ground truth in the parameter grid of our reproduction.

6 CONCLUSION

Regarding our approach to challenge the findings, there are several things that we can say about the various settings we observed. Concerning the ground truth, the chosen value still seems to be arbitrary. Since it is not included in the data generating process it does not change the ranking of the estimators, so for the significance test of difference between the means this can be disregarded. However not including the ground truth in the data generation process seems to be questionable.

Changing parameters that contribute to the simulation of the data lead to significant results in almost every case. The only settings where a 5% threshold for the p-value was exceeded were in simulations that were only replicated 10 times. Since the sample size for

our t-test is considerably small in that case, it is natural that the significance declines.

Overall it was feasible to reproduce the results of the experiment, including priming different parameters. The proposed bias adjusted estimator performed best in all relevant cases, which was confirmed using statistical tests. For further studies, it would be interesting to investigate the integration of the ground truth in the data generating process and its impact on the results.

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